

FORMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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The study of the laws of development of social entrepreneurship in higher education institutions is associated with the need to study the socio-economic situation in the country at the present stage. It should be noted that the development of the economy is characterized by the presence of mass reproduction, the implementation of sustainable changes in the productive forces, specific indicators of growth and development, education, science and cultural life of the country, as well as quality of life.

There are a number of key features that distinguish social entrepreneurship from other types of business:

1. The supremacy of social mission over commercial interests.

In this case, the social impact is not a by-product of entrepreneurial activity, but serves as the main target result, and the resulting profit is largely consistent with the social goals of the company and is not distributed among the owners. A social enterprise is directly designed to significantly eliminate or mitigate real social problems.

2. Innovative approach to solving social problems.

Innovation is inherent in the social entrepreneur as soon as he transforms the existing social order into a more convenient one. Otherwise, the social problem could

already be solved in the traditional way - using the potential of the public, private or non-profit sector.

3. Existence of sustainable commercial influence.

The self-sufficiency of a social enterprise is the basis of its competitiveness. At the same time, it is very important that the income comes mainly from the sale of goods and services, rather than from the support of charitable contributions and grants.

The most important social outcome of the activities of social enterprises is to increase the overall economic efficiency. Within the framework of social entrepreneurship, resources that have not been used before or are not available at all are put into economic circulation. In fact, the field of social entrepreneurship is a new sector of the economy located at the intersection of commercial and non-commercial sectors (Figure 1.5).

Figure 1.5. Social entrepreneurship as a new sector of the economy

Social entrepreneurs are unique in their kind because they are able to work at the intersection of commercial and non-commercial worlds that speak different languages and have different priorities.

According to a number of researchers, the main conditions of social entrepreneurship are experience and content [1].

The experience includes:

personal characteristics and feelings (empathy, sense of justice);

acquired beliefs (influence of upbringing, friends, family, teachers, leaders);

With the availability of support for this activity confident in their ability to provide assistance.

Content is a zone of human interaction with the social sector, in which confrontation with social problems (communication with a dying patient, seeing hungry poor children, stray dogs, etc.).

The implementation of systemic reforms in the economic and social spheres of the country will lead to the formation of a separate "tandem" of priority national projects, which will be achieved by complementing each other with optimal solutions to the tasks of socio-economic development.

The emergence of national projects should be seen as a revolution in attitudes towards state development. At the same time, the projects themselves are vectors that define specific directions of selective advancement to contribute to qualitative changes in the context of renewal occurring in all spheres of life [2]. The actualization of the project approach is associated with the "complexity" of the main directions of strengthening the state, as well as the definition of priorities for future activities beyond the boundaries and boundaries of the tasks of reforming a particular sector.

Today, the idea of national projects has reached a qualitatively new stage of its development, and national projects are the main means of achieving these goals. As for the participation of regions in the implementation of federal projects, it should be done at the expense of "regional projects". Thus, we can conclude that a framework has been created that not only further "encourages" program-oriented management methods, but also allows them to be widely applied in project activities. Adoption of national projects meant the actualization and "reformatting" of the entire system of existing state programs.

The essence of national projects is to provide them with the necessary information for the business about what the state plans to do in the long run, where it intends to invest its resources and what conditions will be created for the emergence of private entrepreneurship.

The national project proposes the necessary measures to support entrepreneurship at all stages of development, from ideas to direct exports. The project targets are to increase the number of people employed in small and medium-sized

businesses, including individual entrepreneurs; an increase in the share of SMEs in the country's GDP, as well as an increase in the share of SMEs' exports in the total volume of non-exports.

Based on the analysis of the passport of the national project "Science" and the first steps in its implementation, it can be concluded that by the end of the period will be established world-class research and education centers, NTI competence centers, as well as research centers and actively cooperates with enterprises of the real sector of the economy. The development of advanced infrastructure for research and development in our country will renew the material and technical base of scientific organizations. In addition, an integrated system of training of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel will be created, the necessary conditions for the professional growth of young scientists will be created. By achieving the project's targets, Russia can make a "technological breakthrough" to increase its competitiveness in the world community [3].

It is obvious that the main national goals cannot be achieved without the participation of large-scale universities in national projects. Universities need to use a variety of tools to promote themselves. For example, they can change the system of governance by business, as well as territorial authorities, in general, by strengthening the necessary cooperation with civil society, which acts as a customer for higher education. Regional universities play an important role as they make a significant contribution to the development of the regional economy and in some regions contribute more than 5 per cent to the gross regional product.

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